

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

Time flies: a year of DATAMITE as seen from every WP

To achieve DATAMITE's ultimate goal of delivering a modular, open source, multi-domain framework to improve data monetising, interoperability, trading and exchange, the different partners of the consortium are organised under Work Packages (WP), forming a total of 7. In this article the **leaders of each Work Package review the first year of DATAMITE (2023) and what they hope to achieve in the next year (2024)**, within their area of work and objectives.

[Read the full article](#)

Campaign: Meet the people Behind DATAMITE

DATAMITE is an ambitious project with a consortium of 26 organisations from 11 countries, but beyond the numbers are the people. **With the**

series "Meet the people behind DATAMITE" we want to introduce the people who work every day to achieve our ambitious goal: to deliver a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve data monetising, interoperability, trading and exchange in the form of software modules, training and business materials for European companies, empowering them to become new relevant players in the data economy.

[Read his full interview](#)

Santiago Cáceres (ITI), Project Coordinator

We present **Santiago Cáceres** from [ITI](#) and **DATAMITE Project Coordinator**. "I have been working in European research funding based projects for around 14 years, and my current interests are around the data cycle, from its generation to its exploitation and going through the transformation, artificial intelligence techniques, and so on", he explains.

Vasso Apostolopoulou (OTE Group of companies)

We present Vasso Apostolopoulou from [OTE Group of Companies](#). As an Innovation Engineer at OTE, her role involves evaluating and testing emerging technologies to align them with OTE's business needs.

[Read her full interview](#)

New YouTube channel

We are delighted to announce the launch of the DATAMITE YouTube channel. We will be sharing information, interviews, updates and much more about the DATAMITE project, an innovative initiative designed to help European businesses and public administrations overcome the challenges of data monetisation.

[Subscribe!](#)

External and Internal events

DATAMITE at the European Big Data Value Forum 2023

The [European Big Data Value Forum 2023](#) took place from the 25th to the 27th of October 2023 in Valencia, Spain. The event, organised by the [Big Data Value Association \(BDVA\)](#), brings together industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policy-makers. **DATAMITE** could not miss the forum and **was present during the three days with a booth, and the session "Technologies enabling the data economy"**, co-organised with its Sister Projects [PISTIS](#), [UPCAST](#) and [FAME](#).

[Read more](#)

DATAMITE at EclipseCon 2023

DATAMITE took part in [EclipseCon 2023](#), organised in Ludwigsburg in October 2023 by the DATAMITE partner, [Eclipse Foundation](#). EclipseCon is the leading conference for developers, architects, and open source business leaders to learn about Eclipse technologies and share best practices. This makes EclipseCon the **perfect scenario for DATAMITE to meet and make itself known among the community**. The project had a poster displayed at the Eclipse Research booth.

[Read more](#)

DATAMITE participates at InfoCom

On December 14th, the IT Innovation Center of [OTE Group of Companies](#) hosted a **session** at the [25th InfoCom World 2023 Conference](#) in

DATAMITE holds its last plenary meeting of 2023

From 21 to 22 November, the **DATAMITE Consortium met in Bologna to host its third -and last of 2023- plenary meeting**. The

Athens **focused on DATAMITE**, called “DATA Monetization, Interoperability, Trading & Exchange”, as part of a scientific workshop entitled as “Modern Research and Development. The project was also **represented within the IT Innovation Center of OTE Group booth**.

meeting, hosted by [CINECA](#), took place over two full days in order to make an in-depth assessment of the progress made during these first 11 months of work and to establish the necessary roadmaps to start producing tangible results for the beginning of DATAMITE's second year of life.

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